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Paper-6

**A Study of Factors Effecting the State of
Peace and Role of Education in Developing
Virtues leading to the State of Peace**

Dr. Ritu Bala

A Study of Factors Effecting the State of Peace and Role of Education in Developing Virtues leading to the State of Peace

Dr. Ritu Bala¹²

Abstract

“Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaye”.

Though education ‘Vidya’ for peace a theme, a topic, which has drawn a sudden attention of anyone on this planet, this has in fact been very important in all the ages. Peace is virtually important in life. It is a crucial link in the chain of life. It is indispensable for creating atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. To maintain peace, the utmost important thing is that the person should have peace of mind, heart and health, hand and socially and economically well adjusted. Education can prove a gateway to peace. This paper has thrown light on the factors effecting peace and how education develops virtues which lead to the state of peace.

Key words- Peace, Education, non-violence, problem-solving attitude, moral values, balanced personality, prosperity, universal brotherhood

Introduction-

Since ancient times, it is said “Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaye” which means with education, we finally attain salvation. Though education for peace a theme, a topic, which has drawn a sudden attention of anyone on this planet, this has in fact been very important in all the ages. How? It is but natural if a question like this emerges in one’s mind. To get an appropriate and benefitting reply to this, it is necessary to comprehend the meaning and nature of peace and education both and that too separately.

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Peace-

The English word peace has originated from the Latin word 'Pax', which in a broad spectrum means a situation free from strain, civil disorders in particular, struggle quarrel spectrum or conflict along with desiring harmony in day to day human practices. From Eastern view point – India, in particular, the word 'Shanti', made o 'Shant' has originated from Sanskrit, which divulges categorically a wish for freedom from physical, social, natural ad spiritual sufferings. The state of peace has been considered extra ordinary. That is why Shanti occupies a proud place in Vedic prayers, illustrated in 'Shanti Prakram' as predominant maxim (Mool-Mantra) calling for peace in every nook and corner of universe:-

*“Om Dyao Shanti Antriksham Shanti Prithvi
Shantirapa Shanti Aushadyay Shanti Vanspataye
Shanti Vishvey Deva Shanti Brahm Shanti Sarvam
Shantireva Shanti Sa Ma Shantirrdhihye
Om Shanti Shanti Shanti Om”*

“Unto the Heaven be peace, unto the sky and the earth be peace; peace be unto the water, unto the herbs and trees be peace; unto all Gods e peace, unto Brahm and unto all be peace and may we realize that peace.”

Therefore, we can conclude from the both eastern and western views about peace that the state of peace is the source of origin of mutual understating, of co-operation and a clarion call for prosperity of one and all – in the larger interest of humanity.

Education-

Now let us find the answer to the second question, what is and how it is related to peace? The word 'Education', 'Vidya' in Hindi and 'Talim' in Urdu has been used in many distinct and different senses, i.e. one as to bring up, to nourish, to draw out and second as an act of teaching or training to individual. Most of us have

familiarity with the second one. Socrates has rightly said that “Education means the bringing out of the ideas of universal validity which are latent in the mind of every man.” Swami Dyanand has supported the value of education as “Education is a means for character formation and righteous living.” In the words of Mahatma Gandhi, “By education I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in child and man – body, mind and spirit.” Draver, “Education is a process in which and by which knowledge, character and behaviour of the young are shaped and moulded.” According to the Report of Indian Education Commission (1964-66) also emphasized, “Education ought to be related to the life, needs and aspirations of the people and thereby made powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation.”

From these definitions we can conclude that education trains a child to think rationally, develops problem-solving attitude, inculcates the virtues of discipline, truthfulness, honesty, non-violence etc. in the students and forms a basis for the prosperity of the people and the nation. We can conclude in the words of T.P. Nunn, “Education is the complete development of individuality so that he makes an original contribution to human life according to the best of his capacity.”

Education for Peace-

“Peace must first be developed (through education) with in an individual. And I believe that love, compassion and atrioms are the fundamental basic for peace. Once these qualities are developed with an individual, he or she is then able to create an atmosphere of peace and harmony. This atmosphere can be expanded and extended from the individual to his/her family, from the family to the community and eventually to the whole world.”

- The 14th Dalai LamaTenzin Gyatso

Doubtless peace is virtually important in life. It is a crucial link in the chain of life. It is indispensable for creating atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. To maintain peace, the utmost important thing is that the person should have peace of mind, heart and health, hand and socially and economically well adjusted.

Education for peace is a process to achieve the state of peace through means of education. In education we learn and train in problem solving method. In this method we firstly recognize the problem and then decide our plan of action and try to find the best solution to the problem. This method may be adapted to education for peace.

Factors - a Curse to Peace-

Let's first recognize the problem why there is need to judge methods to education for peace. In the above discussion we have concluded that education is itself promotes harmonious development of an individual then why even educated persons are also lack this most precious virtue of peace and humanity. We are spending millions and billions to educate our children to make India a developed nation. But to what use? The reason is that we are producing literate machines with no humanity, no feelings and no emotions. We are producing just literate persons but not educated human beings.

Both students and teachers – the two very important pillars of formal education are carrying on the process of education with just minds and not by heart. Even in the famous Bloom's Taxonomy the objectives has been categorized in three domains: Cognitive, Effective and Conative. But in our most important phase of lesson plans for teaching practice in B.Ed. we just concentrate on cognitive domain of instructional objectives and pay no attention to other two domains. This is the reason that we are just producing literate machines and we have to conduct

conferences and seminars on this topic. Our education system is marks and grade oriented not person and humanity oriented. We have to concentrate on the following internal and external factors that have threats to peace:

How to Achieve Peace through Education-

The factors which contribute to this stage of peace are ahimsa-nonviolence, discipline, mutual understanding, cooperation and coordination, high morals, feeling happy and enlightened, problem solving attitude, prosperity and universal brotherhood etc. Education – a science and an art of living is a gateway to peace. To throw more light on this fact, I put forth the following facts in the support of education for peace:

Non-Violence ‘Ahimsa’ and Education-

Peace has its roots in the supreme, eternal and natural human value of non-violence ‘Ahimsa’. Ahimsa is a science for existence and development, an art of living. Education imparts knowledge with the purpose of developing the spirit of duty and responsibility. Education paves the way for conflict resolution with sole interaction of supporting the truth without any confusion or conflict.

Problem-Solving Attitude and Education-

Education develops the problem-solving attitude among students and this attitude helps them to settle inevitable day-to-day problems, disputes and struggles to family, community and society by using the non-violence, peaceful means.

Moral Values and Education-

Swami Dyanand has supported the value of education as “Education is a means for character formation and righteous living.”

Balanced Personality and Education -

Education is helpful in development of high and strong character and personality by inculcating the qualities of self-control, self –reliance, patience, honesty, truthfulness, dutifulness, honesty, loyalty, justice, punctuality, reality etc. moreover, it deprives off the feeling of jealousy, hate etc.

Prosperity and Education-

Education makes child a qualified and useful citizen of the society from the beginning. The person either be a doctor, an engineer, a trader, a businessman, a corporate or a worker, a coolie, a salesman can do well with his/her earning the livelihood only if s/he is trained at least in fundamental values of education. The absence of education leads to conflicts, anxiety and mental disturbance. Formal education resolves such situations and becomes pioneer to achieve prosperity.

Vasudev Katumbkam – Universal Brotherhood and Education-

Any progress in education of a nation when crosses its boundaries, it reaches to international value. The progress in the field of education is neither the achievement of a single person, society, nation, caste or religion followers only nor is the property of a particular nation. Therefore, education not only spreads the message of national brotherhood but also of vasudev katumbkam - universal brotherhood.

From the above discussion, it is proved that education inculcates the virtues of non-violence, problem-solving attitude, discipline, moral values, balanced personality, prosperity and universal brotherhood which lead a person to peace of mind, heart, hand and health and socially and economically well-adjusted and hence creates an atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. Therefore it can be evidently declared that education – a science and an art of living is a gateway to peace.

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